

Ethics guidelines

Deliverable 8.3

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1. Introduction

INNATURE aims to re-imagine and accelerate new living futures and ‘next practices’ across Europe by co-creating five diverse Nature Based Solutions (NBS) demonstration cases across Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania, UK) that are inclusive, beautiful and sustainable, the three key pillars of the New European Bauhaus (NEB). It will do so by bringing biodiversity and people diversity together at all levels (i.e. diverse communities, artists and designers, ecologists, researchers, policymakers, other stakeholders).

The INNATURE project includes data processing, data sharing, and working with potentially vulnerable groups in the INNATURE Eco-Social Living Labs and processing of personal data (see D8.2 Data Management Plan for further details). Thus, this ethics guidelines document is crucial to act as a support in the ethical handling of such data collection, as well as more broadly setting out the ethical values of conducting the INNATURE project related to AI / LLM use, image use and travel impacts etc.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable is part of T8.4., and sets out the INNATURE ethics approach, following the ethics appraisal procedure in Horizon Europe. It sets out ethical principles related to local data collection, data processing and data sharing, working with potentially vulnerable groups in the Eco-Social Living Labs and processing of personal data, including sharing of data outside of the EU (with the UK partners). It sets out procedures for local data collection (obtaining relevant ethical permits) with a privacy notice template, information sheets and consent forms templates (and a personal data risk assessment template) to support project partners to tackle ethical issues and find additional information - see ANNEX I to V.

It will also ensure that all project activities respect human dignity and autonomy, protect participants from harm, and treat communities fairly, handling personal data lawfully and ethically, placing data protection as a fundamental right and central to INNATURE research and project ethics. It also includes INNATURE project values, principles and procedures related to the use of AI, use of general project images and visual material, and project travel. In Appendix V a risk assessment template is also provided for researchers working in the field to understand and minimise risks to ensure their own safety.

2. Ethical principles for the project

In INNATURE, we are committed to following generally acknowledged rules of ethical research and applying the ethical standards and guidelines for Horizon projects throughout the project.

The following Tables 1 to 4 provide a summary of the main ethical issues identified in different work packages. There are no activities anticipated that cause potential harm to humans or to the environment during or beyond the project. However, the use of AI and our travel activities do have an impact on the environment and need to be carefully considered. Note that this document and table are dynamic and updated as per the project progresses.

Table 1. Main identified ethical issues per WP related to data collection.

Involvement of volunteering participants		
Ethical issue	Mitigation measure	WP
Gathering data on people-diversity needs	Participatory protocols are developed in each WP	WP2
Gathering data from local stakeholders in each country		
Gathering textual and visual data through local co-creation conversations with local communities, organisations/associations, businesses, institutions, ecologists, who will participate in Arts Conversations	Local Arts Conversations framework / protocol will be developed to facilitate the process in each Demo Case	WP3
Gathering graphic and oral accounts (recording and transcriptions) from semi-structured interviews with artists, art-leads and researchers	Common interview guidelines will be developed for implementation in each Demo Case.	WP3
Gathering video recording data from Art Network meetings via semi-structured interviews conducted with selected strategic stakeholders: each demo-case conducts 2-3 interviews based on a shared interview-guide.	Common interview guidelines will be developed, local consent/ethics data stored locally, textual interview summaries fully anonymised will be available to be shared across countries.	WP3
Involvement of vulnerable groups		
Emotional distress, cultural sensitivity, confidentiality, stigmatisation, and equitable inclusion	“Inclusive participatory practice” considerations will be defined in each Demo Case by pre-assessing the potential risk based on participants’ profile and background.	WP2, 3 & 6
Processing of personal data		
Data collected from volunteering participants during workshops in Eco-Social Living Labs through interviews, surveys, spreadsheets and illustrations. Audio & video recording of Living Lab implementation and activities. Data of INNATURE partners.	Data quality checks before processing, fully anonymised before being provided open access, while sensitive data containing personal information will remain confidential. The processes of informed consent, anonymisation and pseudonymisation are planned prior and in collaboration with data protection officers/services in each Demo Case, with special considerations whenever vulnerable groups of people are involved. All personal data will be handled and shared in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and institutional data protection policies. See also D8.2.	WP 2-7
User-generated images from biodiversity app	Summaries available to all, analysis by Natuurpunt is allowed, raw data are depending on the permit of the observers.	WP4 & 5
User-generated data (citizen science observations); reporting on maintenance issues, feedback, recording, sharing of anonymised images, sharing of anonymised videos.	All sensitive data will be anonymised automatically by Crowsora, who will provide the repository, and the data will be available for viewing via the digital platform.	WP5
Open data	Publicly available data could be reused with CC BY, ODC (EU), or OGL (UK) licences, provided attribution is given. Images will be shared under a Creative Commons licence (CC BY or equivalent) to allow responsible reuse.	ALL

When AI or LLMs (Large language Models) are used, each partner must always consider carefully if a machine is needed with its associated environmental and ethical impacts to do our brain work - there need to be clear reasons to justify. Each individual to discuss with the WP lead about its use and to be raised up to the Executive Committee if extensive use of AI / LLMs are considered, prior to usage. No open AI / LLMs can be used due to copyright / IP issues. Some examples below of potential AI/LLM use in INNATURE.

Table 2. Main identified ethical issues per WP related to AI.

Use of Artificial Intelligence-based systems		
Ethical issue	Mitigation measure	WP
App-based nature observations facilitated by AI driven automated image recognition with NIA (Nature Identification API)	Responsible partner, Natuurpunt, will ensure compliance with European legislation when using AI. Results outputs will be discussed and validated by ecological experts.	WP4
Image anonymisation by Crowdsora	All data that is anonymised by Crowdsora will be anonymised with an efficient pre-trained YOLO model that is hosted in Crowdsora AWS account. Third-party AI systems won't be used for this purpose, which reduces the resources (energy, water, etc.) that are used in the process.	WP5
Use of AI/ LLMs in writing, editing and summarising documents	The agreed INNATURE approach will be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First considering if the use of AI/ LLMs is really necessary, given its environmental and ethical impacts. Discuss with WP lead. • If considered absolutely necessary, only closed (paid for) models can be used and not the open free version due to IP / copyright issues of text. • AI / LLMs could be used to assist in e.g. transcribing text (e.g. interviews), translating text or summarising parts of our own text - but its usefulness versus its environmental impact always needs to be carefully weighted and justified. • However, the use of AI /LLM generated text always needs careful checking manually by a human and no blind transfer can be used. • AI /LLM use always needs to be acknowledged and its environmental impact always needs to be carefully weighted and justified. 	ALL
Use of AI for images or graphics or visuals or drawings	Generally, not anticipated to be used in the INNATURE project. If considered locally, it needs to be discussed and agreed among WP leads on a case-by case basis. Always to be carefully considered due to limitations, ethical issues and environmental impacts and for it be properly justified. If AI generated images or visuals are used, the origin will be explicitly expressed and the grounds for use justified.	ALL
Any other use of AI / LLMs	Prior to the use of any AI / LLM models, partners will discuss their implications and agreed on a common way of using it.	ALL

Table 3. Main identified ethical issues per WP related to general image use.

Use of project images		
Ethical issue	Mitigation measure	WP
Images showing people / children	<p>We are collecting general images of NBS and NEB processes during INNATURE activities but also related to our general work, that enables the INNATURE project to use as ‘stock photos’ for broader communication and dissemination purposes.</p> <p>It is difficult to produce a simple checklist on what is the ethical use of photos. Instead, we practice collectively ethical literacy. It means skills to navigate ethical dilemmas and having the language to describe our decisions. These skills include critical thinking, situational awareness, and cultural sensitivity.</p> <p>For example, as a general rule, it is legal to take photos of people in public spaces where there is no reasonable expectation of privacy. However, we aim that the people who are recognisable in the photos that INNATURE uses for communication, have been informed and do agree with the use of the photos. In the case of children on photos, consent from their parent is given.</p>	ALL
IP (Intellectual property) and Copyright of images	Any images shared are only shared with own copyright and IP held with INNATURE partners. We do not use copyrighted images by others, unless CC-Y-BY and creator acknowledged.	ALL

Table 4. Main identified ethical issues related to INNATURE project travel.

Project travel		
Ethical issue	Mitigation measure	WP
Local travel for project activities	The consortium have agreed to travel with the least carbon intensive travel option (e.g. walk, cycle, tram, train, bus), where possible in relation to local project distances travelled.	ALL
International travel	<p>Over-land travel is preferred over flying, however due to distances and travel time and costs this will not be realistic in many cases and hence flying will be needed.</p> <p>Not all partners will attend all international project meetings and hybrid events so that online attendance is possible, will be created where needed.</p>	ALL

2.1 Ethics and research integrity

In addition to adhering to relevant regulations and guidelines, good research practices are embedded within project workflows. The Grant Agreement Annex 5: Ethics (Article 14) requires following the highest standards of research integrity. We have drafted the following listing of good research practices to ensure the realisation of this requirement.

- In alignment with the NEB, NBS design must consider not only environmental performance but also who benefits and who does not, and whether beauty and aesthetics are culturally respectful and non-excluding, and also actively work to include vulnerable user groups.

- Participation is voluntary, providing clear, accessible information and informed consent forms according to literacy level, language, and context.
- Participants can withdraw at any time (with clear explanation about data processing).
- Each Demo Case lead will identify and mitigate risks (see D8.1 Risk and Quality Plan) and ethical issues related to data collection (see [Table 1](#) and [Table 2](#)), including emotional distress, stigma, social conflict, surveillance concerns, or unintended ecological impacts.
- We will avoid data misuse by carefully data collection planning and collecting only essential data for the implementation of the project.
- Provide transparent information about how data will be collected, used, stored, shared, and deleted - see Data Management Plan (D8.2.); each INNATURE project partner to keep the DMP data collection 'Excel' data collection and management library up to date throughout the project.
- We will document decisions, risks, mitigations, and data governance in compliance with GDPR and as part of D8.1 Risk and Quality plan.
- Each partner to comply with agreed ethical values and procedures related to AI, general image use and project travel (see [Table 2](#), [Table 3](#) and [Table 4](#)).
- We will closely collaborate with Data Protection Officers across all stages, especially for sensitive, large-scale processing or non-EU data transfers (UK).
- We will ensure compliance with national and local legal requirements, and coordinate with local ethics committees where needed.
- These Ethics Guidelines (D8.3) will be revised and updated if needed accordingly.

The work of INNATURE researchers is further guided by the fundamental principles of research integrity as outlined in [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity by ALLEA](#):

- **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis, and the use of resources.
- **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way.
- **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment.
- **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

Crucially, prior to starting any INNATURE project action or task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities.

2.2 Ethics management in INNATURE

In INNATURE, research ethics is of crucial importance in all scientific and innovation activities. The project will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national laws on ethical principles. We respect the integrity and dignity of persons. In our activities, we recognise the rights of individuals to privacy, personal data protection, and freedom of movement.

Ethics management is part of Management Work Package 8 (Task 8.4), led by Tampere University. Each partner and demo-case leader ensures that they obtain relevant ethical permits and statements from Ethical Committees to carry out research. Locally applicable information sheets and informed consent forms will be provided for participants in all Eco-Social Living Labs and participant’s informed consents obtained in accordance with local criteria (for examples see ANNEX). All personal data will be properly protected according to GDPR, and the necessary data processing and data sharing agreements are as per procedures set out in D8.2 Data Management plan.

Together with the Coordinator, a local Ethics manager in each demo case oversees and is responsible for the implementation of the project work in adherence to the Ethics Guidelines (this document) and applicable regulations (Table 5) and as per D8.2. Data Management Plan. Table 5 will be updated and added to as the project develops.

Each researcher involved in the project is responsible for conducting research and other project activities following the highest ethical standards. Project partners who are gathering and processing personal data as part of INNATURE activities, are responsible for contacting their organisation’s Data Protection Officer (DPO) to ensure that personal data is lawfully processed and that all the necessary agreements are in place.

Table 5. Main national legislations, guidelines and regulations - will be updated throughout the project.

Name	Description	Country (Context)
Regulation (EU) 2024/1689	It lays down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act).	ALL
The Finnish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2023 (RI Guidelines)	Research conducted in Finland to follow principles of reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability, covering the entire research lifecycle to prevent misconduct.	Finland
Data Protection Act (1050/2018)	It supplements the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) providing the national legal framework for processing personal data in Finland.	Finland
Nature Conservation Act (9/2023)	It aims to protect biodiversity, natural beauty, and promote sustainable use of natural resources in Finland.	Finland

Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2026)	It sets national standards for responsible research conduct, including honesty, transparency, accountability and respect.	Denmark
Danish Data Protection Act (Databeskyttelsesloven)	It supplements the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).	Denmark
Danish National Committee on Health Research Ethics (VEK)	While project activities are not expected to fall within the scope of the Danish VEK (it does not involve clinical trials or research on human biological material), it has been considered to make sure we safeguard participants’ privacy.	Denmark
Law no. 206/2004 on good conduct in scientific research, technological development, and innovation	This law sets up the standard for research integrity in Romania, in particular in relation to academic fraud (plagiarism, fabrication, falsification), which is part of Romania’s compliance of The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.	Romania
UK General Data Protection Regulation and Data Protection Act 2018	Main UK legal framework for processing personal data, including lawful basis, fairness & transparency, data minimisation, storage limitation, security, data subject rights, data sharing and retention. Relevant to interviews, focus groups, workshop records, photographs, transcripts & any identifiable participant data.	UK
Data (Use and Access) Act 2025	Updates parts of the UK data-protection framework, including provisions relevant to scientific research processing. It should be read alongside the UK GDPR and Data Protection Act 2018.	UK
The Concordat to Support Research Integrity	UK framework for research integrity, research ethics and governance. Relevant principles include honesty, rigour, transparency and open communication, care and respect, and accountability.	UK
Children Act 1989, Children Act 2004, and Safeguarding Vulnerable Groups Act 2006	Relevant if the project later involves direct engagement with children, young people, or vulnerable adults. At this stage the Sheffield ethics application states that no direct student contact is foreseen, but this should remain a trigger point for further review if youth engagement develops.	UK
Environment Act 2021 and Natural Environment and Rural Communities Act 2006	Relevant to biodiversity, nature recovery, public bodies’ biodiversity duties, and the wider legal context of nature-based solutions.	UK
TBC	All EU applicable standards and legislation are adhered to and additional applicable national or regional specific guidelines and standards will be followed and added as the project progresses.	Belgium

3. Data processing and data sharing

3.1 Principles of data protection

Data processing and sharing in INNATURE will be framed within the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), specially as per the key principles defined in Article 5, Regulation 2016/679. As also set out in D8.2 Data Management Plan, we will ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects,
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes,
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed,
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date,
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and,
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

We will not grant open access to personal data on the condition that it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the project as per the Grant Agreement. If this is the case, we will ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation, and the persons whose data are transferred to the granting authority is informed accordingly.

3.2 Importing/exporting data

Transfers of data will be carried out through approved channels using required security measures. Where necessary, the project's partners will cooperate in order to enable one another to fulfil legal obligations arising under applicable data protection laws (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) within the scope of the performance and administration of INNATURE and of the Consortium Agreement. In particular, partners will arrange a separate data processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.

Sharing of personal data outside the EU or with the UK partners is not foreseen in INNATURE. However, any sharing of personal data will be carried out lawfully, fairly and transparently under both the EU and UK General Data Protection Regulation (EU and UK GDPR). Key considerations include:

- Definition of the role of the involved parties, i.e. is this a Data Controller to Data Processor relationship, and which organisation is which? Controllers establish the purpose and means of processing, and processors act on behalf of the controller.
- Establishing a written contract (often in the form of a separate Data Processing Agreement) with a processor as per GDPR Article 28. For controller-to-controller sharing, a data sharing agreement is highly recommended, though not legally required.

- Data subjects must be informed about how and with whom their data is shared, typically via privacy notices.
- Appropriate preventative measures must be in place, such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) or adequacy decisions. This may result in additional contractual documentation being required.
- Definition of appropriate security measures when needed to ensure compliance with EU and UK GDPR standards.
- Clarifying “open” access.
- Align data sharing strategy with funding requirements.
- Use trustworthy data repository, data archives and/or data centres.
- Select an appropriate licence for reuse and clarify user rights.

3.3 Processing of public data

In INNATURE, we acknowledge that even if publicly available data is used for training purposes (e.g., data published on YouTube), it does not mean that such data can be freely used. It is a common misconception in data privacy that if information is “publicly available” (e.g., on LinkedIn, public Instagram profiles, or government registries), it is “fair game” to collect and use. From a privacy compliance perspective, public data is still personal data and so processing it may entail significant legal risk under the EU GDPR. Key considerations when processing of public data:

- Even though data is ‘public’, it does not exempt it from protection and it needs to be processed within a valid Legal Basis (Article 6, GDPR).
- When personal data is not obtained directly from the participant, the controller must follow Article 14 of the GDPR and give the participant all the required information.
- Data will not be used for a different purpose than it was made.
- Ensure the processing of personal data that is “necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party. To do so, we will use Guidelines 1/2024 on processing of personal data based on Article 6(1)(f) GDPR¹.

¹ Guidelines 1/2024 on processing of personal data based on Article 6(1)(f) GDPR. Available at: https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2024/guidelines-12024-processing-personal-data-based_en

4. Involvement of human participants

Engaging different people in the project activities is essential for INNATURE to reach its objectives. Involvement of humans will take place in the Eco-Social Living Labs and further details of the potential ethics-related issues are provided in [Table 1](#), [Table 2](#) and [Table 3](#).

Participatory co-creation is one of the fundamental concepts of INNATURE, through which multiple actors (ecologists, artists, designers, other stakeholders) will work hand-in-hand with local communities to deliver NBS that are NEB-by-design across diverse socio-ecological contexts. Human participant involvement, including from vulnerable population groups (incl. children & youth, older people, disabled persons, immigrants, lower socio-economic communities, etc.), is therefore crucial to INNATURE's core project activities and knowledge creation processes (Eco-Social Living Labs, Arts Conversations, uptake of the integrated digital platform, citizen science approaches to climate and biodiversity monitoring) and ultimate delivery, maintenance and progression of INNATURE NBS that are NEB-by-design. All the participants' participation will in all cases be fully voluntary and based on informed consent. We do not foresee any negative impacts or risk of stigmatisation for the participants, as in all activities we will strive to protect the autonomy, wellbeing, safety and dignity of all research participants.

4.1 Collecting of personal data

Collecting, processing, storing and potential sharing of data will be done according to relevant legislation and regulation ([Section 2.2](#)). Strict adherence to EU GDPR regulation will be assured when dealing with personal data. INNATURE also follows responsible research principles and Recommendations of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK for Research Integrity Advisers². ANNEX IV contains a personal data collection risk assessment reflection template.

4.2 Informed consent

Information sheets and informed consent forms will be provided for participants in all Eco-Social Living Labs in the local language - examples in English are provided in the ANNEX. Participants will receive an information sheet and oral info about the research project in their own language and terms they can understand. Each participant involved in the project's activities and the responsible researcher will sign two copies of a consent form including:

- detailed info about the aims, methods and implications of the project,
- who will benefit from the results,
- methods,
- protection of privacy & confidentiality,
- nature of voluntariness, and the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequences,
- relevant national and international ethical research standards and data protection regulations,

² Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) guidelines available at: <https://tenk.fi/en/advice-and-materials>

- info on responsible researchers: names, research organizations and contact information.

Consent forms will be stored in local storage where all partners have access control to data at least with user/password and authenticator apps, in some cases with different level accessibility depending on the type of data being processed or two factor authentication.

Personal and other sensitive information will be stored on adequately encrypted drives or in approved cloud storage services such as TEAMS. Further encryption will be applied where applicable (e.g. for special categories or personal information). Organisational guidelines and requirements will be followed.

See also D8.2 Data Management Plan for more detail.

4.3 Data protection and privacy

All personal data will be properly protected according to the GDPR, and the necessary data processing and data sharing agreements will be put in place at the start of the project. As key principles:

- To the degree possible, data will be pseudonymised and anonymised before being shared among the consortium. Fully anonymised data will be provided open access, while sensitive data containing personal information will remain confidential.
- For activities involving human participants, the processes of informed consent, anonymisation and /or pseudonymisation are planned beforehand.
- The INNATURE project uses Zenodo, which implements open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval - <https://zenodo.org/communities/innaturecollective/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

ANNEX I. Example of a privacy notice used at Tampere University

The example privacy notice is what researchers self-archive and fill in prior to conducting data analysis and is made available to participants.

Privacy notice (13.01.2022) for scientific research

EU General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679), art. 12, 13, 14

1. Title, nature and duration of research

Title of research: INNATURE: Enhancing Biodiversity and Social Inclusion by Transforming Europe's Living Environments

Case study

Follow-up study

Duration of research: 01.08.2025- 31.08.2029

Duration of data processing: See the Data Management Plan D8.2. Archiving of anonymised data (text) with [\[to be filled\]](#).

2. Data Controller

Research will be conducted in an employment contract with [\[to be filled\]](#), indicating the [\[to be filled\]](#) to be the data controller.

[\[to be filled with Institution Name\]](#)

[\[to be filled with address\]](#)

Business ID: [\[to be filled\]](#)

Data Protection Officer of [\[to be filled\]](#)

3. Principal investigator or research group

The Principal Investigator is a person assigned by the Data Controller to oversee the implementation of the research project. A research group may also be assigned to serve as the Principal Investigator.

Name: [\[to be filled\]](#)

Contact details (email + phone): [\[to be filled\]](#)

4. Researchers

Please indicate the persons who will carry out the research activities. If the project is collaboratively conducted, please list the researchers from each partner organisation.

Members of the research project team

Name + contact details (email + phone): [\[to be filled\]](#)

5. Content of research records

The personal data to be processed by categories includes names, contact information, and voice, photographs. The interviews focus on *[to be filled]*

6. Sources of personal data

Data will be collected from the participants via *[to be filled]*.

7. Purpose of processing personal data

The purpose of processing personal data is **scientific research**.

This research is part of the project INNATURE: Enhancing Biodiversity and Social Inclusion by Transforming Europe's Living Environments, funded by the European Union.

Our project aims to re-imagine and accelerate new living futures and 'next practices' across Europe by co-creating five diverse Nature Based Solutions (NBS) demonstration cases across Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania, UK) that are inclusive, beautiful and sustainable, the three key pillars of the New European Bauhaus (NEB). It will do so by bringing biodiversity and people diversity together at all levels (i.e. diverse communities, artists and designers, ecologists, researchers, policymakers, other stakeholders).

We do this through *[fill in METHODS]* where members of the public in case study locations in Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania and the UK take part / tell us in detail about *[to be filled]*

This will help to create a fairer future where the negative impacts of greening the city are understood and managed while its benefits are scaled-up and applied elsewhere

8. Lawful basis for processing personal data

The lawful basis for processing is the EU General Data Protection Regulation Article 6 Paragraph 1 and the Data Protection Act (1050/2018) 4 §:

- Public interest or the exercise of official authority
- Scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes
- Archiving of materials relating to research or cultural
- Other, please specify:

9. Sensitive personal data (special categories of data and criminal records)

- No sensitive personal data will be processed during the research project
- The following types of sensitive personal data will be processed during the research project:
 - Racial or ethnic origin
 - Political opinions
 - Religious or political beliefs
 - Trade union membership
 - Genetic data

- Biometric data to uniquely identify a person
- Health data
- Data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation

Will personal data concerning criminal convictions and offences be processed during the research project?

- No
- Yes

Lawful basis for processing of sensitive personal data:

The lawful basis for processing is EU General Data Protection Regulation, Articles 9 (special categories of personal data) and 10 (personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences), and the Data Protection Act (1050/2018) 6§ and 7§

- Consent of the data subject
- The processing activities relate to personal data that has been manifestly made public by the data subject
- The processing activities are conducted for the purpose of scientific or historical research in the public interest, for statistical purposes, or in connection with the exercise of official authority
- The processing of personal data is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest

10. Transfer of data to external parties (Transfer means that some other party will process personal data and return the results to data controller)

Personal data will be regularly transferred to parties other than the members of the research group.

Please describe the type of data that will be transferred, the recipient and the legal grounds for transferring personal data: *If needed, transcription will be undertaken by an external party with a long track-record in research related transcriptions.*

11. Transfer or disclosure of data outside the EU/EEA

Will data stored in the research records be transferred to a country or an international organisation that is located outside the EU/EEA?

- No
- Yes, please specify (contact always Data Protection Officer):

Description of the measures taken to protect data:

Note: *if data to be transferred a separate agreement will be made and DPO advise sought in both countries.*

12. Data protection principles

Protection of manual materials (e.g. paper documents):

- In a locked room
- In a locked cupboard
- Other, please specify:

Protection of digital materials (e.g. information systems and equipment):

- usernames
- password
- multi-factor authentication (MFA)
- access management (IP address)
- collection of log data
- physical access control
- other, please specify

Processing of data that directly identifies an individual:

- Directly identifiable data will be removed during the analysis stage
- The materials will be pseudonymised
- The materials will be analysed without removing directly identifiable data, because (please provide the reasons for retaining personally identifiable data): Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

Protecting data in transit:

- secure transmission, please specify: Data files will be only accessed and shared via software solutions authorised by Tampere University.
- file encryption, please specify: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.
- other, please specify: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

13. Processing of personal data after the research project has been concluded

- The research records will be destroyed
- The research records will be anonymised and archived without personally identifiable data
- The research records will be archived without anonymisation

The research data are offered for permanent archiving without personal data at the [\[to be filled\]](#). The Archive may hand over the data for reuse to registered clients for research only.

14. Data subjects' rights and possible restriction thereof

Data subjects have the following rights under the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

- Right of access

- o Data subjects are entitled to find out what information the University holds about them or to receive confirmation that their personal data is not processed by the University.
- Right to rectification
 - o Data subjects have the right to have any incorrect, inaccurate or incomplete personal details held by the University revised or supplemented without undue delay. In addition, data subjects are entitled to have any unnecessary personal data deleted from the University's systems.
- Right to erasure
 - o In exceptional circumstances, data subjects have the right to have their personal data erased from the Data Controller's records ('right to be forgotten').
- Right to restrict processing:
 - o In certain circumstances, data subjects have the right to request the University to restrict processing their personal data until the accuracy of their data, or the basis for processing their data, has been appropriately reviewed and potentially revised or supplemented.
- Right to object
 - o In certain circumstances, data subjects may at any time object to the processing of their personal data for compelling personal reasons.
- Right to data portability
 - o Data subjects have the right to obtain a copy of the personal data that they have submitted to the University in a commonly used, machine-readable format and transfer the data to another Data Controller.
- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority
 - o Data subjects have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority in their permanent place of residence or place of work, if they consider the processing of their personal data to violate the provisions of the GDPR (EU 2016/679). In addition, data subjects may follow other administrative procedures to appeal against a decision made by a supervisory authority or seek a judicial remedy.

Contact information:

Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman

[to be filled]

The Data Controller follows a GDPR-compliant procedure for responding to subject access requests.

ANNEX II. Example Information sheet used at Tampere University

This example information sheet is what researchers write prior to conducting data analysis and is made available to participants in advance of their participation. They need to be given the opportunity to ask questions, as it forms the basis upon which they sign the informed consent sheet to take part in the study (see ANNEX III).

Participant Information Sheet

INNATURE: Enhancing Biodiversity and Social Inclusion by Transforming Europe's Living Environments

You are being invited to take part in the INNATURE research project that aims to re-imagine and accelerate new living futures and 'next practices' across Europe by co-creating five diverse Nature Based Solutions (NBS) demonstration cases across Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania, UK) that are inclusive, beautiful and sustainable, the three key pillars of the New European Bauhaus (NEB). It will do so by bringing biodiversity and people diversity together at all levels (i.e. diverse communities, artists and designers, ecologists, researchers, policymakers, other stakeholders).

We do this through [\[Fill in METHODS\]](#) where members of the public in case study locations in Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania and the UK take part / tell us in detail about [\[to be filled\]](#)

Your participation will be an important contribution to the project. Everyone has a story to tell and we want to speak to as many different people as possible about this.

After reading this information sheet, you will have the opportunity to ask any questions you may have. You will be separately requested to provide consent for participating in the study.

Purpose of the research

There are two main purposes to this research part. First, [\[to be filled\]](#). Second, we want to use these accounts to help the policy makers designing cities to understand [\[to be filled\]](#).

This will help to create a fairer future where the negative impacts of greening the city are understood and managed while its benefits are scaled-up and applied elsewhere.

Description of the process

If you decide to participate you will be invited to take part in [\[DESCRIBE\]](#) which will take about x hour and be audio-recorded. The [interview/workshop/?](#) is an opportunity for you to share your experience and you will be free to discuss what seem to you to be the most important issues.

You will also be invited to be present on photographs during the workshop, but we will only include them in the project with your consent.

Procedures for collecting research data

The participants will be *interviewed*. The *interviews* will be transcribed for research purposes. Transcription will be done by the *researchers / a transcription service*. In addition, participants will be asked whether they are happy to appear on photos to be used on the project website or publications (e.g. newsletter, academic journals). In addition to the researchers conducting the interviews, artists, ecologists and ecologists and other experts are involved in the project *and there may be later workshops for which you will be asked informed consent*.

Potential risks and benefits of participation

The results of this study will be used in research that aims to co-create NBS.

The procedures and methods used during this study do not involve health risks, social risks, or financial risks. Data is carefully managed to ensure the security of personal data.

Data confidentiality, processing and storage

All personal data collected during the study will be processed in compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the data protection laws of *[to be filled]*.

Data about individual participants will not be disclosed to external persons.

Privacy protection in the context of research papers and communicating about the study

All *interviews* will be anonymised to protect the privacy of participants.

The results will be reported in exhibitions (physical and online), publications, presentations and to inform discussions about a fairer future for home heating between members of the public and those responsible for the design of our future energy systems.

Use of data for non-research/later research purposes

The anonymised research data *transcriptions will be archived at the Finnish [to be filled]* for reuse in research or scientific theses including dissertations and master's theses.

Funding sources

This research project is funded by the European Union, Grant agreement ID: 101181560.

Voluntary participation

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw from the study at any time either permanently or for a temporary period.

Inquiries

Please direct all inquiries about the study to

[CONTACT NAMES]

(leave a copy with the participant)

ANNEX III. Example informed consent template used at Tampere University

This example Informed consent form is what researchers make available to participants in advance of their project participation, alongside providing the information sheet (see Annex II) and once any questions they have, have been answered.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Consent for participation in a research study part of INNATURE: Enhancing Biodiversity and Social Inclusion by Transforming Europe's Living Environments

I have been requested to participate in the research study identified above. I have received information about the study in writing and have had the opportunity to ask questions from the researcher(s) conducting the study.

I understand that participating in the study is voluntary. I am aware that I have the right to refuse to participate and the right to withdraw from the study permanently or for a temporary period at any time and without giving a reason. I understand that any personal data collected in the course of the study will remain confidential.

Participant details

Full name:

Phone number:

Email address:

Consent for use of photos taken during the interview /workshop with respondents' permission

- I consent to the use of photos taken during the interview,
 I do not consent to the use of photos taken during the interview.

Consent for archiving interview/text at the Finnish Social Science Data Archive

- I consent to the archiving of my interview/text at the Finnish Social Science Data Archive for reuse in research or scientific theses including dissertations and master's theses.
 I do not consent to the archiving of my interview/text at the Finnish Social Science Data Archive.

Permission to contact

I give the INNATURE project permission to contact me regarding the interview and related outputs.

- Yes
 No

I hereby give my voluntary consent for participation in this study (two copies to be signed- one to keep by the participant)

Place and date

Signature

ANNEX IV. Risk assessment

This risk assessment is a template to fill in directly related to working with participants and collection of personal data as part of the different project activities. Thus, this risk assessment should be completed before undertaking any activity entailing personal data collection.

Project title: INNATURE

What kinds of risks are associated with processing personal data in different phases of your research? Processing personal data refers to all processing activities during the lifespan of your project, such as collecting, saving, analysing, storing, disclosure, archiving, deleting or erasure of data. Assess risks and consequences from the perspective of your data subjects. Think, for example:

- Who are processing data in the different phases of the research?
For example: *Research data will be processed by the members of the research team during all phases of the research. Data will be transcribing by researchers themselves, meaning that no separate data processing agreement is required.*
- Where the personal data will be stored and in which format? For example: *Data will be stored on university laptops and phones, audio recorders, TUNI OneDrive cloud storage and a jointly used Teams environment. Access is granted only to research team members and laptops and phones are protected by passwords and MFA.*
- How are personal data transferred in different phases of the project?
For example: *Recorded audio files are transferred from recording equipment either by uploading or wired connection to TUNI OneDrive cloud storage. Data will then be deleted from recording equipment. Files will be transcribed and anonymised.*
- What is the scope of processing, are various personal data combined and are special categories of data³ being processed?
- For example: *Data will be collected as part of the recorded interviews which will then be stored, transcribed, and anonymised in line with Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD) guidelines. Non-anonymised files will be deleted after anonymisation. At the end of the project, the anonymised transcripts will be offered to the FSD for archiving. No special categories of data are being processed.*

Also check the [risk assessment guidelines and examples](#) before completing a risk assessment.

³ Personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation, or data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood	Severity	Measures to diminish the risk	Residual risk ⁴
Unauthorised access to data	Possible	Identified impacts	Training researchers in security of data processing,	Low
Hacking of software environments used	Possible	Identified impacts	Only using TAU approved software and environments	Low
Loss of laptops/phones containing data	Possible	Identified impacts	Careful handling of devices, laptops protected by passwords and MFA	Low
Data breach when transferring to transcription service	Possible	Identified impacts	Use of TAU's primary service provider	Low
Data breach when transferring data	Possible	Identified impacts	Transfer of data with software authorised by TAU, use of wired connections	Low
Participants being recognisable from interview transcripts	Possible	Identified impacts	Thorough anonymisation of interview transcripts in line with FSD guidelines	Low
	Choose from drop downlist	Choose from drop downlist		Choose from drop downlist

Summative assessment of the data protection risk: Low

If your risk assessment indicates that your processing activities are likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, you will be required to carry out a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

Risk assessment indicates the project may not have need for DPIA
Risk assessment indicates the project may have a need for DPIA

If the projects appears to have a need for DPIA or you are not sure, please contact the local Data Protection Officer (at TAU: dpo@tuni.fi)

⁴ Remaining risk refers to the risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects after the necessary protection measures have been implemented.

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ANNEX V. RESEARCHERS' FIELD DATA COLLECTION - Risk Assessment Form

This risk assessment is a template to fill in directly related to identify, and assess the risk level, of the potential hazards related to any activity in which researchers need to conduct field data collection.

Examples of Potential Hazards:

1.	Fall of person (from work at height)	6.	Lighting levels	11.	Use of portable tools / equipment	16.	Vehicles / driving at work	21.	Hazardous fumes, chemicals, dust	26.	Occupational stress
2.	Fall of objects	7.	Heating & ventilation	12.	Fixed machinery or lifting equipment	17.	Outdoor work / extreme weather	22.	Hazardous biological agent	27.	Violence to staff / verbal assault
3.	Slips, Trips & Housekeeping	8.	Layout, storage, space, obstructions	13.	Pressure vessels	18.	Fieldtrips / field work	23.	Confined space / asphyxiation risk	28.	Work with animals
4.	Manual handling operations	9.	Welfare facilities	14.	Noise or Vibration	19.	Work with lasers	24.	Condition of Buildings & glazing	29.	Lone working / work out of hours
5.	Display screen equipment	10.	Electrical Equipment	15.	Fire hazards & flammable material	20.	Radiation sources	25.	Food preparation	30.	Other Hazards specific to your work.

PERSONS AT RISK: Employees (nr?) Contractors (nr) Public (?) Visitors (?) Students (?) Others (?)		Task Description			
RISK (H) High (M) Medium (L) low (O) No Risk		Environment: (where?)			
TASK or ACTIVITY:		INITIAL RISK LEVEL			FINAL RISK LEVEL
Significant Hazard (examples in grey)	Potential Consequences of Hazard (examples in grey)		Existing Control Measures (examples in grey)	Additional Control Measures (If Required) (examples in grey)	
<i>Visiting unfamiliar places in urban or rural areas</i>	<i>Researchers could get lost or wander into lonely or 'out of the way' areas.</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>Researchers to prepare and map route; to not wander into lonely areas where they are unfamiliar with the surroundings.</i>	<i>Contact mobile phone number of colleagues and destination to be handy</i>	<i>L</i>
<i>General danger of traffic and other hazards associated with visiting urban areas en route to locations</i>	<i>Being hit by vehicles, causing a road traffic incident</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Researchers to be aware of traffic when crossing, taking photos, and looking after cameras and other valuables.</i>		<i>L</i>

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<i>Being the subject of street crimes</i>	<i>Theft of valuable belongings and mugging</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>keeping valuables out of sight when not in use.</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Slips and trips, falling</i>	<i>Bruises, scratches, broken bones and sprains from uneven or slippery surfaces or entering a floor void</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>wear sturdy footwear; assess situation prior to going into certain spaces; ensure any equipment put in place is taped and wires tidied to avoid others slipping/tripping.</i> <i>Clear signage where tripping hazards remain or exist; ensure floorboards sturdy.</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Exposure to inclement weather</i>	<i>Exposure and in extreme cases hypothermia</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>Researchers to wear warm and where possible water-proof clothing; reduce exposure time; use taxi transport.</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Lone working</i>	<i>Researchers are vulnerable to other risks and external forces, incl. verbal assault</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Researchers to not work alone wherever possible. If they are to work alone, they must inform another researcher to act as 'buddy' - ensure data protection includes 'buddy' in permission.</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Heavy lifting</i>	<i>Vulnerable to injuries from lifting heavy items / instruments</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Researchers /artists to ensure items can be carried safely, to lift with assistance and to pack items in easy to carry weights.</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Hygiene illness risks</i>	<i>Participants exposed to covid (other illnesses and thereby expose participants</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Participants to not work when ill; to wear masks and abide by local/ national /university COVID guidelines</i>		<i>L</i>
<i>Driving in unknown rural areas in possibly challenging conditions (snow, fog, ice, darkness)</i>	<i>Causing or being involved in road traffic accidents</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Check weather and road conditions, prefer public transportation or taxis in challenging road/weather conditions</i>		<i>L</i>
				Overall Risk:	<i>L</i>
Comments:					

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Additional References, Tasks Etc			
Researchers have to read, print and sign this assessment.			
Undertaken By:		Revision Date:	
Other Persons Consulted:		Revision Date:	
Date:		Revision Date:	

Use the table given on the risk matrix to score your hazard or activity for the probability ('L') likelihood harm will occur and the severity ('S') of the outcome.

Risk Score = S X L		SEVERITY OF OUTCOME (S)			
		Minor	Serious	Major	Fatal
LIKELIHOOD (L)	Very Unlikely	1	2	3	4
	Unlikely	2	4	6	8
	Possible	3	6	9	12
	Likely	4	8	12	16

Risk Level	
Low	
Medium	
High	
Very High	

Plot the scores on the matrix or multiply them together (LxS) to obtain a risk score - then use the colour of that score to determine the Risk Level, Low to Very High. Activities that are High or Very High must not start (or will need to be suspended), without appropriate controls in place to reduce the risk to an acceptable level. Wherever it is a possibility that a serious injury may occur risk must be lowered by putting in extra control measures.

ANNEX VI. List of Tables

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Table 3. Main identified ethical issues per WP related to general image use.6

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